

in a randomized block design with four replications. Jaya rice seedlings (34-d-old) were planted in 20-m² plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Granular insecticides were applied as basal; emulsifiable insecticides were sprayed as needed.

Because of an unusual dry spell, thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* damage occurred at initial tillering; GM was significant only at maximum tillering. Carbofuran as basal alone or with quinalphos spray gave excellent protection against thrips, but not against GM (see table). This may be because the healthier plants in carbofuran-treated plots were more vulnerable to GM than the plants damaged by thrips.

Granular quinalphos treatment produced the highest yield. Spray application of quinalphos was best for GM control. □

Effect of insecticide on GM in rainfed lowland rice in Sambalpur, Orissa, India.

Treatment	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Thrips damage ^a at 25 DT	Silvershoot ^b (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Carbofuran 3 G basal	1.0	0.0	32.8 (34.8)	2.7
Quinalphos 5 G basal	1.0	2.0	13.1 (21.0)	3.3
Quinalphos 25 EC spray at 25 DT	0.5	4.0	3.5 (10.6)	2.9
Monocrotophos 40 EC spray at 25 DT	0.5	3.5	7.1 (15.4)	2.9
Carbofuran 3 G basal + quinalphos 25 EC spray at 25 DT	1.0 + 0.5	0.0	33.6 (35.3)	2.8
Quinalphos 5 G basal + monocrotophos 40 EC spray at 25 DT	1.0 + 0.5	1.5	12.7 (20.5)	3.1
Control		4.0	9.1 (16.6)	2.8
LSD (0.05)		—	7.3	ns

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice. ^bFigures inside parentheses are transformed values.

Effect of sequential neem treatment on green leafhopper (GLH), rice tungro virus (RTV) infection, and predatory mirid and spiders in rice

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In 1987 wet season, we tested a package of neem seed kernel extract (NSKE) treatments on IR42 rice.

The package involved soaking seeds in a 10% NSKE solution, dipping of seedling roots for 12 h in a 5% NSKE

solution, and spraying a 4% NSKE solution emulsified with 1% Teepol at 150 liters/ha 6 times at 10-d intervals from 5 d after transplanting (DT). The neem package was compared with monocrotophos sprayed at 0.75 kg ai/ha. Plot size was 50 m²; each treatment had 7 replications. Field populations of GLH, RTV, and predatory mirid and spiders were sampled visually at 10-d intervals from 8 DT; RTV incidence was recorded 25, 45, and 65 DT.

GLH populations in all treated plots were significantly lower than in untreated plots at 28 DT (Fig. 1). However, predatory mirid and spider populations also were significantly lower in insecticide-treated plots than in neem-treated plots 48 DT. RTV infections in treated plots were not significantly different (Fig. 2). □

Leafhopper nymphs, adults, and predators (no.)/20 hills

1. GLH (a) and predatory mirid and spider populations (b) recovered from 8 to 48 DT on neem- or insecticide-treated plots, IRRI, 1987 wet season. Av of 7 replications. Lines with a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

RTV infection (%)

2. Percent RTV infection on plots treated with neem or insecticide, IRRI, 1987 wet season. Av of 7 replications. Bars with a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Storing dry *Beauveria bassiana* mycelium

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The insect fungi (Deuteromycotina: Hyphomycetes) that commonly infect rice insects such as brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) can be isolated on artificial media and mass-produced. Mycelium and conidia of the fungi conventionally are produced by solid fermentation (mycelium growth and sporulation occur on solid substrates) or by diphasic fermentation